

Improving The Methodology of Using Mobile Technologies in Improving the Quality of Education

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Abstract

In this article, the importance, role and achievements of mobile education in the rapidly developing era are highlighted with the help of examples. In addition, the article describes the necessary methods of mobile education and pedagogical forms of mobile education in order to improve the quality of education.

Key words: computer, education, digital education, teaching, linguistics, technology

The idea of a "book-sized computer" was first put up by American scientist Alan Key, who worked in the field of computing systems theory, in the 1970s. Information about the use of mobile devices and Intel Classmate computers for children for remote education based on WiMAX wireless network is reflected in the research work. Additionally, the problems of teaching computer science in mobile computer systems were examined in M.A. Grigoryeva's research works, and the structure of teaching linguistics and mathematics using mobile systems was examined in Saville-Smith, G. Stead, and G. Solley's projects. In Australia, Great Britain, Italy, Canada, Cyprus, Mexico, New Zealand, Poland, USA, Turkey, Chile, Sweden and South African countries, educational technologies based on internal information and telecommunication tools (mobile computer systems: phone, tablet

and smartphome) are widely available.¹ Nowadays, the effective use of mobile devices in the fields is expanding more and more. At the same time, the possibility of mobile devices, as education and innovative research are progressing, their widespread use as an educational tool is taking the main place in traditional and non-traditional education. Mobile devices can be utilised to access the remote education platforms that are being developed. A contemporary approach to education is mobile technology-based learning, which is evolving daily. As an illustration, we can mention that all universities moved to online learning, or remote learning, during the quarantine procedure that was implemented in our Republic in 2020 (covid-2019). We can state that the majority of students utilised mobile phones for efficient distant learning during this time. Mobile devices can be used for a greater variety of things beyond only making calls and sending texts. These days, a lot of people may get information, learn new things, and share ideas thanks to these technologies. In fact, there are numerous definitions of mobile learning, or m-learning, available today. These tools remain one of the main tools for students to get information. Students want to always have access to educational resources on smartphones or tablets. From distance learning to computerized e-learning, online learning, online learning, and more, there are many terms used to describe Internet-based learning. We define e-learning as courses taught specifically over the Internet, where the professor teaches outside the classroom. Not a lesson distributed by DVD or CD-ROM, videotape, or television. It is interactive because you can communicate with your teachers, professors or other students in your class. Sometimes it's a live broadcast where you can "electronically" raise your hand and communicate in real time, and sometimes it's a pre-recorded lecture. There will always be a teacher or

¹ Attewell J., Savill-Smith, C. Mobile technologies and learning. - London: Learning and Skills Development Agency, 2004.- p.47-53.]

professor who will be in touch with you and grade your assignments and tests. elearning has proven to be a successful method of education and is becoming a way of life for many people. Nowadays, it is much easier to connect to the Internet through mobile phones than to connect to the Internet through a personal computer. Mobile communication companies provide customers with the opportunity to use the Internet (MB, GB) together with talk time. You can use the Internet services from anywhere you want using a convenient mobile phone. As a result, the demand for using the Internet is increasing day by day.

Research of pedagogical forms of mobile teaching in education

Because digital technologies are mobile, they alter the physical relationships between educators, students, and educational buildings, opening up intriguing possibilities for new kinds of education. The flexibility required for this new kind of connection is beyond the scope of even traditional distance learning, which is why interest in "mobile learning" is developing. Inevitably, the process starts as a technological solution created for a different purpose, searching for an issue in education that it can address. This procedure has been repeated so frequently in the history of educational technology that it is not the best outcome for learning because teachers require resources that take control of educational research, clearly state our needs, and apply them to assess new technologies according to our criteria. When defining a pedagogy for mobile education, it is necessary to clearly understand what exactly mobile education brings, what is new and how it differs from previous educational technologies. Features such as the following probably do not reflect this, as they are also true for many other technologies:

Ensure that students develop their knowledge in a variety of contexts. Allow students to develop understanding

Mobile technologies often change the educational work model. the educational process is aimed at:

- students and their personal relationships (peers, teachers, etc.),
- what the student is learning (topic, relation to previous experience, etc.) and
- where and when students learn, we are unlikely to easily distinguish mobile learning from any other form of distance learning.

Twenty years ago, a skilled technologist would have been conversant with all of these definitions. Wikipedia's definition of e-learning, for instance, recognises that it shares similarities with distance learning and e-learning, but also believes that its unique quality is "focusing on learning in a variety of contexts using mobile devices"—perhaps reading a book on the bus. It is obvious that further research has to be done to pinpoint the essential elements that set it apart. The fact that this new motivator is now the main emphasis of what mobile learning may offer is another encouraging feature. Students that use mobile learning appear to appreciate the practice. In particular, effective forms of motivation provided by aspects of mobile education can be described as follows:

- control (over goals);
 - ownership;
 - interesting;
 - communication;
 - learning in context;
 - continuity between contexts
- Mobile learning is important for access, personalization, engagement, control of learning, ownership and ability to demand things, respect for student rights.

Features such as control, ownership, and peer interaction help explain why mobile learning can be "fun." "Learning in context" and "continuity between contexts" are also aspects of ownership and control, which explain why these characteristics make learning easier and more effective. How does mobile technology support learning? Mobile technologies are unique in offering site-

specific digital learning that encourages ownership and control. What does this mean students actually do? Collaborative learning and mobile learning together offered a wide range of educational activities that can be supported by mobile digital tools and environments:

- research - the actual physical environment associated with digital applications;
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- discussion - with peers, synchronous or asynchronous, audio or text;
- recording, data acquisition - sounds, images, videos, texts, locations;
- construction, creation, simulation - use of obtained data and digital tools;
- exchange - obtained data, digital construction and simulation products;
- testing - products created in comparison with other products, reviews of others or actual physical environment;
- adaptation - all of these activities are possible in other forms of e-learning, but for mobile learning it may be important how they are integrated to best support the learning process.

To test this idea, we turn to the next section, which addresses the pedagogical challenges of mobile learning and tests it against the requirements of an optimal learning experience. What are the pedagogical problems associated with mobile learning? The goal of turning to new technologies is to find a pedagogy that supports learning better and is more robust than traditional methods. By trying to understand what is required to master complex ideas or higher-level skills, we can design pedagogies that can initiate the cognitive activities that students need to perform in order to achieve the intended learning outcomes. According to the structure, the dialogic process between the "teacher" and the "student" is determined at two levels:

the discursive level, where attention is paid to the construction of theory, concepts, descriptions, and the empirical level, where the main focus is practice, activity.

Both levels are interactive, but at the discursive level the interaction takes a communicative form - the teacher describes: that is, the teacher decides what to "frame", the student asks questions, the teacher clarifies, the student expresses an idea or concept. Discussion-level interaction benefits from reflective learning. In the same way, a teacher can create a learning environment that is tailored to the needs of the students and benefits from their reflection on student achievement. Based on a number of findings from studies of student learning, it can be interpreted that teaching methods should encourage students to engage in all of these different cognitive activities if the learning outcome is comprehension or mastery. In this sense, it should be a basis for designing the educational process.

- Students may be interested in thinking about theory if they need to use it to navigate the environment to achieve the goal of the assignment;
- They are more motivated to repeat their actions, if the feedback about their actions is internal, that is: show the result of your actions in such a way that it is clear how it should be improved;
- They are more encouraged to reflect on this experience if they are required to present some version of their idea to the teacher at a discursive level - depending on the discipline this is traditionally an essay, report or model. The same goes for peer-to-peer collaboration
- students are encouraged to improve their practice if they can share their results with their peers;
- and if they can reflect on their experiences in discussing their experiences with their peers, they are motivated to improve their practice and deepen their conceptual understanding.

Mobile learning technologies offer exciting new opportunities for teachers to engage students in challenging environments of active learning through sharing, sharing ideas, exploring, learning, experimenting, discussing, but not without guidance and support. To get the most out of the experience, the complexity of the instructional design must be rich enough to match these rich possibilities. This method offers teachers a way to plan optimal learning models that take full advantage of mobile technologies.

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